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*THE SOCIAL MEDIA USE TO PROMOTE FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP: A
BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY¹*

**O USO DE MÍDIAS SOCIAIS PARA PROMOÇÃO DO
EMPREENDEDORISMO FEMININO: UM ESTUDO BIBLIOMÉTRICO**

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ABSTRACT

Even with the intensification of social media use in small and medium-sized businesses led by women in Brazil, the benefits of using these resources are little known in literature and business practices. This research filled this gap, identifying studies on social media use per female entrepreneurship. For this, a bibliometric study was carried out, in which 45 articles were found in the Web of Science database, and these were analyzed with the VOSviewer software. As a result, there is an increased number of articles on the topic, as well as quality in these publications. Five groups were formed to analyze keywords and present research trends. This research contributes theoretically by systematizing and analyzing studies that relate social media to female entrepreneurship, promoting Sustainable Development Goal 5 on gender equality and female empowerment. In practice, it demonstrates the need to use social media to gain competitiveness in businesses led by women.

Keywords: female entrepreneurship, social media, bibliometric study, bibliometric.

RESUMO

Mesmo diante da intensificação do uso de mídias sociais nos pequenos e médios empreendimentos liderados por mulheres no Brasil, os benefícios de uso desses

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recursos são pouco conhecidos na literatura e na prática empresarial. Esta pesquisa preencheu este gap, identificando os estudos que relacionam o uso de mídias sociais no empreendedorismo feminino. Para isto, foi realizado um estudo bibliométrico, no qual foram encontrados 45 artigos na base Web of Science e estes foram analisados com o software VOSviewer. Como resultado, há um crescimento do número de artigos sobre o tema, assim como há qualidade nestas publicações. Foram formados cinco grupos na análise de palavras chaves, apresentando tendências de pesquisas sobre o tema. Essa pesquisa contribui teoricamente ao sistematizar e analisar estudos que relacionam mídias sociais ao empreendedorismo feminino, promovendo o Objetivo de Desenvolvimento Sustentável 5, sobre igualdade de gênero e empoderamento feminino. Na prática, demonstra a necessidade do uso de mídias sociais para ganho de competitividade em negócios liderados por mulheres.

Palavras-chave: empreendedorismo feminino, mídias sociais, estudo bibliométrico, bibliometria.

INTRODUCTION

Marketing's primary objective the needs and desires of consumers, and to achieve this it develops a series of activities to attract and satisfy them (Kotler & Keller, 2012). A current trend in marketing is balancing this overall objective of exchange with the impact of consumption on society. Therefore, companies need to reinvent their practices and adapt their strategies to consumer expectations - one such strategy involves addressing issues related to sustainable development (Lopes & De Souza Freitas, 2016).

In attracting and retaining consumers, the field of marketing is increasingly focused on creating a superior value proposition, since consumers are now more discerning and do not merely choose a product or service, but rather a proposition that aligns with their lifestyle and is consistent with the values they believe in (Kotler & Keller, 2012).

Organizations must adapt to new concerns about sustainable development in general, as consumers are more cautious and seek more information about what they consume and who produces what they consume

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(Kotler & Keller, 2012). In the pursuit of demonstrating value to the customer, companies no longer simply promote what they do, but also their values. To communicate this information, they use multiple media channels, with social media being a common tool (Khang, Ki & Ye, 2012).

Recent studies highlight some contributions of social media use to women's entrepreneurship, or their main characteristics (Fontana et al., 2021; Da Silva, Lasso & Mainardes, 2016). However, these are isolated studies and do not provide deeper knowledge on the subject. This study seeks to fill this gap, helping to build knowledge about the use of social media by women entrepreneurs. It also contributes to understanding the main communication and marketing practices that foster the promotion of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with special attention to SDG 5, which addresses gender equality and women's empowerment (Portal ODS, 2023).

The purpose of this article is therefore to identify the main scientific productions over the past 10 years on a marketing trend - the use of social media - that can be applied to the promotion of women's entrepreneurship. In doing so, it contributes to theory by highlighting and analyzing research that connects social media use and women's entrepreneurship, while also pointing out research trends on the subject. In managerial practice, it demonstrates that social media use is essential for women entrepreneurs.

The structure of this article begins with the presentation of objectives and a literature review on women's entrepreneurship and social media. Next, it describes the methodological procedures adopted for carrying out the bibliometric study. Following that, the results and data analysis are presented. Finally, the article outlines theoretical and practical contributions, limitations, and suggestions for future research.

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LITERATURE REVIEW

To achieve the objective of gathering information on the themes used in the bibliometric study, a literature review was carried out, divided into the topics (1) Women's Entrepreneurship and (2) Social Media.

Women's entrepreneurship

For a long time, women's primary role was to take care of the family and household. Over time, however, women began to seek recognition in the labor market, with entrepreneurship emerging as one of the options. According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM, 2023), Brazil stands out for its high rate of women entrepreneurs, ranking 7th among 54 countries analyzed.

Many women attempt to balance their personal and professional responsibilities. While many entrepreneurs are aware of their economic role, a considerable number are still responsible for managing the household and raising children. Powell and Eddleston (2013) report that family support, for both men and women, is directly linked to entrepreneurial success.

The crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic disproportionately affected women, placing them at the center of waves of unpaid work overload. There has not been a single day without news highlighting the negative impacts of COVID-19 on people's health, the economy, and mental well-being. The pandemic exerted significant pressure on business owners, self-employed workers, and formal employees, with many individuals seeing their livelihoods and basic comforts threatened (Stephan, Zbierowski & Hansard, 2020; Vendramine, Nobre & Vieira, 2021). As with any period of crisis, driven by rising unemployment and poverty, necessity-driven entrepreneurship grew as the only viable means of financial survival for individuals and families (Seredkina, Burova & Ganina, 2020). This reality was even more evident among women, who were most affected by the economic recession caused by COVID-19 and who turned to

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entrepreneurship as a solution to balance demands with income generation (UN Women, 2020).

In this context, it is important to recognize the progress of women in entrepreneurship. Many entrepreneurs, in order to succeed, rely on a series of tools in their businesses, among which digital marketing plays a fundamental role - as will be seen in the next section on the use of social media.

Social media

We are all immersed in a culture characterized by the use of digital information and communication technologies (ICTs). In recent years, this topic has gained prominence in academic and business discussions, associated with different levels of understanding of technology use: at the individual level (individual competence), at the organizational level (core competencies), and at the national level (educational systems and skills development) (Fleury & Fleury, 2000).

In contemporary times, communication and people's influence in media flows have expanded. The internet and, particularly, the emergence of digital social networks have allowed the development of more segmented communities and the instant exchange of information, as Bennett (2014) pointed out - leading to the need for understanding social media use.

In recent decades, social media has become the subject of various studies due to its increasing importance in the dissemination of information and communication, being responsible for changing the way people interact (De Souza Costa et al., 2016).

The resources available in social media also present advantages over offline media: they are easier to measure and involve lower costs. The amount paid to an advertising company to post on social networks, using them as a medium, is minimal compared to other options such as radio and TV (Gomes &

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Mondo, 2016). The advantages of being able to measure the results of companies' publications include reputation management, customer support, brand protection, benchmarking, market research, brand exposure, marketing research, campaign measurement, audience segmentation, influencer mapping, lead generation, and innovation, among others (Pinochet, Pachelli & Da Rocha, 2018).

Another important fact is the use of social media by companies, which has become indispensable to achieving competitive advantage in the market, proving to be an effective tool for customer acquisition, in addition to facilitating the marketing of products and services, promoting the growth of companies that use it (Dos Santos et al., 2019).

Within this scenario, women entrepreneurs also use information and communication technologies (ICTs). According to SEBRAE, 81% of the businesswomen surveyed have internet access and use it in their businesses mainly to: promote the company (52%), showcase products (48%), and conduct online sales (25%) (SEBRAE, 2018). It is noteworthy that businesswomen are actively present on social media: 43% have a Facebook page, 71% use WhatsApp to communicate with customers, and 53% believe their company's sales have greater potential for growth in the next five years through the internet and social networks (SEBRAE, 2018).

Data from the GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor) survey indicate that the percentage of entrepreneurs in Brazil increased by 11.6% over the past 10 years, representing 38% of the Brazilian population in 2018. It is evident that social media has contributed to opportunity-driven entrepreneurship (GEM, 2023), meaning that it has also stimulated women's entrepreneurship, even if indirectly.

Methodological procedures

To achieve the article's objective of identifying the main publications on women's entrepreneurship and social media, a bibliometric study was carried out. Bibliometric studies in the applied social sciences involve analyzing the production of articles, mapping academic communities, and identifying research networks through the creation of indicators to highlight institutions (Okubo, 1997).

This research adopted the methodology of Chueke and Amatucci (2015), which consists of five steps for conducting the study, as presented in Chart 1.

Chart 1 – Steps for Conducting the Bibliometric Study

Steps	Description
Step 1: Develop the Research Protocol	Develop the research protocol by establishing the questions that should be answered through the systematic reading of articles. Define the outputs or displays that will be presented in the article.
Step 2: Identify the Most Relevant Studies in the Field	Initially, it is suggested to conduct a broad search in different databases and journals to identify relevant articles. For this purpose, inclusion and exclusion criteria for articles should be created. These search criteria must be aligned with the research question and the ongoing discussion in the field of knowledge.
Step 3: Assess the Quality of the Studies Collected	Create an article evaluation form with the criteria that will determine whether the article will or will not constitute part of the body of articles to be analyzed exhaustively.
Step 4: Synthesize the Data Collected	This phase consists of tabulating the results, qualifying them, and exploring the contradictions and affinities among the studies.
Step 5: Integrate the Results Obtained	Generate analyses by comparing and contrasting the data. The aim is to answer the research question and suggest new directions for future research.

Source: Adapted from Chueke and Amatucci (2015).

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

This study used articles published in journals in the field of social sciences to achieve the objective of identifying publications on the topic of *social media use and female entrepreneurship*. To identify the most relevant studies,

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data were collected from the Web of Science database, as this database provides tools that facilitate the execution of bibliometric studies. Data collection was carried out on March 11, 2024.

The keywords searched were “social media” and “female entrepreneur”, using the “Topic” option, which allowed for the selection of publications containing these keywords in the title, abstract, or keywords. The filter applied was the selection of journals in the “Business and Economics” category.

As a result, 45 articles on the topic were identified, considering publications from the past ten years. After extracting the data from the database, the articles were evaluated, and the results were tabulated to meet the proposed research objective. Finally, VosViewer software was used to complete the bibliometric analysis and to highlight trends, as well as limitations and suggestions for future research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the methodology presented, the results will be shown in five stages: a) survey of the total number of publications per year on the topic; b) survey of the articles, number of citations, and most influential authors; c) presentation of the journals in which the most influential articles were published; and d) analysis of interactions between keywords and authors in VosViewer

Survey of the total number of publications on the topic

The total number of publications between 2014 and 2024 on the topic “The use of social media for the promotion of female entrepreneurship” was 45 publications. A decline was observed in 2020; however, there was growth in 2021, reaching a peak in 2022 and 2023, with 10 publications in each year. This increase demonstrates that the topic has gained traction in the literature and is

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becoming consolidated as a recurring subject, as it has maintained an average of more than 10 publications in the field since 2022 (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Number of publications per year on the topic

Source: The authors (2024).

Survey of the most influential articles on the topic

Among the 45 articles, the most cited was "Democratizing Entrepreneurship? Digital Technologies and the Internationalization of Female-Led SMEs," with 240 citations. Table 1 lists all articles in descending order. All publications received a total of 1,098 citations between 2014 and 2024.

Table 1 – Number of citations per article / Quantidade de citações por artigo

Article Title	Citations
Democratizing Entrepreneurship? Digital Technologies and the Internationalization of Female-Led SMEs	240
Discrimination, Social Capital, and Financial Constraints: The Case of Viet Nam	158
Barriers to rural women entrepreneurs in Oman	146
Contributions of the use of Virtual Social Networks for Female Entrepreneurship	123
Keeping up the pace of digitalization in small businesses-Women entrepreneurs' knowledge and use of social media	119
The Effect of Business Environment and Entrepreneurs' Gender on Perception of Financial Risk in The Smes Sector	113
A fact or an Illusion: Effective social media usage of female entrepreneurs	102
Impact of COVID-19 on Entrepreneurship and Consumer Behaviour: A Case Study in Saudi Arabia	97
Women MSMEs in times of crisis: challenges and opportunities	80
The Power of Instagram in Building Small Businesses	71
Entrepreneurship Education and Graduates' Entrepreneurial Intentions: Does Gender Matter? A Multi-Group Analysis using AMOS	69
Entrepreneurship research in the Middle East and North Africa: trends, challenges, and sustainability issues	67
Strategic use of digital promotion strategies among female emigrant entrepreneurs in UAE	66
I'm a stay at home businesswoman: an insight into informal entrepreneurship in Jordan	64
Gender and international entry mode	54
Women Managers and Entrepreneurs and Digitalization: On the Verge of a New Era or a Nervous Breakdown?	50
Determinants of innovation decisions among Emirati female-owned small and medium enterprises	46
Is it all just lip service?: on Instagram and the normalisation of the cosmetic servicescape	35
Economic empowerment of Iranian women through the internet	28
Social commerce affordances for female entrepreneurship: the case of Facebook	26
Gender, technology and decision-making: insights from an experimental conjoint analysis	22
Exploring women entrepreneurs' motivations and challenges from an institutional perspective: evidences from a patriarchal state in India	21
Social media's impact on the empowerment of women and youth male entrepreneurs in Egypt	19
Social capital and business performance: a study of female-owned SMEs in the Nigerian informal sector	18
The royal award goes to ... : Legitimacy processes for female-led family ventures	18
Factors effecting female startupper in Hungary	16
Social media entrepreneurship as an opportunity for women: The case of Facebook-commerce	15

Careers of commercially successful female entrepreneurs in context of underdeveloped markets and weak institutions	14
Impact of social media participation on female entrepreneurs towards their digital entrepreneurship intention and psychological empowerment	12
Empowerment of women's entrepreneurship in family business through Twitter	11
Gender stereotype perception, perceived social support and self-efficacy in increasing women's entrepreneurial intentions	8
Knowledge Sharing Enablers in Small Business Networks	7
Social Media as a New Opportunity for Female Entrepreneurs: An Analysis of the Fashion Industry	6
Improving the social performance of women-led microenterprises: The role of social media marketing actions	5
Promoting female entrepreneurship in tourism for sustainable development	5
Female founders in post-socialist contexts: A case study of female founders and owners of media businesses in Kyrgyzstan	3
Do social interactions foster household entrepreneurship? Evidence from online and offline data from China Family Panel Studies	3
Role of passion in entrepreneurial responses to crises on social media platforms	2
Social media adoption by women entrepreneurial small businesses	2
Gender identities and corporate social responsibility practices: a biographical approach of managerial recompositions in SMEs context	2
The impact of entrepreneurs' perceptions and social media usage on their intention to formalise their MSMEs in Egypt	0
Shaping entrepreneurial gender play: Intersubjectivity and performativity among female entrepreneurs	0
The pain of an entrepreneur? Relationship between personality, life satisfaction, and psychological suffering of Brazilian entrepreneurs during Covid19 Pandemic	0
Factors Affecting the Success of Women Entrepreneurs in Egypt	0
Set in motion. Paradoxical narratives of becoming Swedish digital media influencers	0

Source: The authors (2024).

Among all the articles, seven have more than 100 citations and were chosen for analysis. The seven articles selected for citation analysis are presented in Table 2, listed from the most cited to the least cited, in descending order. The columns display the title of the scientific publication, the authors, and finally, the total number of citations accumulated across the three periods. The seven publications account for 1,002 citations, representing 91% of the total citations in the analyzed period.

Five authors were found to have two publications, while the others have one publication each. The five authors are: Albena Pergelova and Desislava Yordanova (authors of the most cited article presented in Table 2), Adnan Maalaoui, Hadia Fakhreldin, and Rania Miniesy.

Although the publication dates of these articles range from 2014 to 2024, they remain influential, as the number of citations continues to increase in the years following their publication.

Table 2 – Number of citations and year of publication for selected articles

Article Title	Author	Citations	Year
Democratizing Entrepreneurship? Digital Technologies and the Internationalization of Female-Led SMEs	Pergelova, Albena; Manolova, Tatiana; Simeonova-Ganeva, Ralitsa; Yordanova, Desislava	240	2019
Discrimination, Social Capital, and Financial Constraints: The Case of Viet Nam	Tho Pham; Talavera, Oleksandr	158	2018
Barriers to rural women entrepreneurs in Oman	Ghouse, Suhail; McElwee, Gerard; Meaton, Julia; Durrah, Omar	146	2017
Contributions of the use of Virtual Social Networks for Female Entrepreneurship	Fontana, Darah de Mathias; Oliveira, Deyvison de Lima; Ramos, Elder Gomes; Massaro, Ariadne dos Santos	123	2021
Keeping up the pace of digitalization in small businesses- Women entrepreneurs' knowledge and use of social media	Olsson, Anna Karin; Bernhard, Irene	119	2021
The Effect of Business Environment and Entrepreneurs' Gender on Perception of Financial Risk in The Smes Sector	Kozubikova, Ludmila; Homolka, Lubor; Kristalas, Dimitris	113	2017
A fact or an Illusion: Effective social media usage of female entrepreneurs	Genc, Merve; Oksuz, Burcu	103	2015

Source: The authors (2024).

The three most cited articles were: (1) by the authors Pergelova, Albena, Tatiana, Simeova-Ganeva, Ralitsa, Yordanova, Desislava (2019), titled “Democratizing entrepreneurship? Digital Technologies and the Internationalization of Female-Led SMEs”, with 240 citations (12% of the total).

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Next, (2) the article by the authors Tho Pham and Talavera, Oleksandr, titled “Discrimination, Social Capital, and Financial Constraints: The Case of Viet Nam”, with 158 citations, representing 8%. (3) The article by the authors Ghouse, Suhail, McElwee, Gerard, Meaton, Julia, and Durrah, Omar, titled “Barriers to rural women entrepreneurs in Oman”, with 146 citations (7% of the total).

Together, these three articles total 544 citations (49.5% of the overall total). This number highlights the relevance of these three scientific publications on the topic within the analyzed period.

Further analyzing the articles with more than 100 citations, we find: (4) the article “Contributions of the use of Virtual Social Networks for Female Entrepreneurship”, with 123 citations (6%). Finally, the articles (5) “Keeping up the pace of digitalization in small businesses – Women entrepreneurs' knowledge and use of social media” with 119 citations, (6) “The Effect of Business Environment and Entrepreneurs' Gender on Perception of Financial Risk in The SMEs Sector” with 113 citations, and (7) “A fact or an Illusion: Effective social media usage of female entrepreneurs”, with 103 citations.

Main journals in which the most influential articles were published

Table 3 presents the journals where the 45 articles were published. The journal with the highest number of publications was the International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research with 5 publications (11%). Next, the journals Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Journal of Family Business Strategy, International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship, and Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies each had two publications (4%).

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Table 3 – Journals in the area of social sciences referring to the sample of 45 publications

Journal	Publications	%
International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research	5	11
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	2	4
Journal of Family Business Strategy	2	4
International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship	2	4
Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies	2	4
Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship	1	2
Electronic Markets	1	2
World Conference on Technology, Innovation and Entrepreneurship	1	2
International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation	1	2
Euromed Journal of Business	1	2
Revista Ciencias Administrativas	1	2
World Development	1	2
Journal of Entrepreneurship and Public Policy	1	2
International Journal of Knowledge Management	1	2
Small Enterprise Research	1	2
Journal of Enterprising Communities-people and Places in the Global Economy	1	2
Social Media: the good, the bad, and the ugly	1	2
Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship	1	2
International Journal of Emerging Markets	1	2
Journal of Competitiveness	1	2
Journal of East European Management Studies	1	2
Social Responsibility Journal	1	2
Economics & Sociology	1	2
Scandinavian Journal of Management	1	2
Advances in Gender and Cultural Research in Business and Economics	1	2
International Journal of Innovation	1	2
Journal of Small Business Management	1	2
International Journal of Organizational Leadership	1	2
China Economic Review	1	2
International Small Business Journal-researching Entrepreneurship	1	2
Technology Innovation Management Review	1	2
Gender Work and Organization	1	2
Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development	1	2
Journal of Services Marketing	1	2
Marketing and Management of Innovations	1	2
Journal of Family Business Management	1	2
Gender in Management	1	2

Source: The authors (2024).

Table 4 presents the research area and classification of each journal. This information was taken from CAPES' Sucupira portal to provide additional information, such as the quality assessment of the publications.

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Table 4 – Classification of journals with the highest number of publications

Journal	Field	Classification
International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research	Public and Business Administration, Accounting and Tourism	A1
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	Public and Business Administration, Accounting and Tourism	A1
Journal of Family Business Strategy	Public and Business Administration, Accounting and Tourism	A3
International journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship	Public and Business Administration, Accounting and Tourism	A2
Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies	Public and Business Administration, Accounting and Tourism	A2

Note: Data on each journal were accessed from the Capes Sucupira portal on 06/06/2024 (<https://sucupira.capes.gov.br/sucupira/public/consultas/coleta/veiculoPublicacaoQualis/listaConsultaGeralPeriodicos.jsf>).

The Classification column shows how CAPES's Sucupira Portal classifies journals, with A1 being the highest rating and A4 the lowest within the A stratum. In this research, all the articles fall within this classification. Journals ranked as "A" demonstrate high-quality research, in this case on the topic of social media use and female entrepreneurship. In social media, examples such as Technological Forecasting and Social Change explore digital influence on consumer behavior and online interactions. In female entrepreneurship, journals such as the International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research investigate the barriers and enablers for women entrepreneurs. These publications in A-rated journals demonstrate the quality of the works selected in the bibliometric study.

Interaction analysis

To analyze the interactions among the selected studies, the VosViewer software was used for data analysis. Based on the dataset extracted from the Web of Science, it was possible to analyze the co-occurrence of keywords across

the studies. A total of 190 keywords were found, and by applying a filter requiring at least two occurrences, a sample of 20 keywords was selected. With this selection, five clusters were identified, forming five groups that reveal the relationships among the selected keywords. The result is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Co-occurrence of keywords in VosViewer

Source: The authors (2024)

The clusters formed were named according to the keywords with the highest occurrence, as follows:

1. **Social Media:** grouped the terms connected with the keyword social media, which appeared nine times. The related terms included the location of the studies, such as Egypt, and then words referring to female entrepreneurship in general, such as women entrepreneurship, small businesses, and women entrepreneurs.

2. **Social:** connected words referring to social issues of female entrepreneurship, such as social capital and informal economy, linked with the term female entrepreneurs, which had the highest number of occurrences in this group, with six citations.

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3. General Entrepreneurship: this cluster was formed with more generic words on the theme of this bibliometric study, such as entrepreneurial intention, social media entrepreneurship, women entrepreneurs, and crisis.

4. Gender: the words with the highest number of occurrences in this cluster were entrepreneurship (nine occurrences) and gender (four occurrences). These main words were connected with female entrepreneurship, female, and entrepreneurship education.

5. Entrepreneurship and Innovation: this group associated the terms entrepreneurs, SMEs, and innovation, without linking them to expressions related to the female context.

Although the keyword analysis was carried out with terms appearing two or more times, it resulted in five clusters that highlight issues addressed in the study, such as: the general theme of entrepreneurship, the use of social media related to female entrepreneurship, a group emphasizing the female gender, another highlighting the social aspects of female entrepreneurship, and finally, a group linking entrepreneurship with innovation.

CONCLUSION

The study achieved its goal of identifying the main scientific outputs of the last 10 years on the use of social media and female entrepreneurship. It presented an overview of the number of publications and citations, as well as identifying the most influential articles and authors. The increase in publications in recent years demonstrates the growing interest in discussing this topic.

This scientific research contributes theoretically by systematizing and analyzing studies that relate social media to female entrepreneurship, filling a gap in the literature. This mapping adds knowledge to more recent studies on the use of social media for female entrepreneurship (Fontana et al., 2021; Da Silva; Lasso; Mainardes, 2016).

Moreover, this research aligns with studies that highlight female entrepreneurship as a necessity after the pandemic, a period in which women were affected by the economic crisis and found in entrepreneurship an opportunity for work (Seredkina; Burova; Ganina, 2020; UN Women, 2020). Finally, it reinforces the notion that understanding the use of social media is essential for entrepreneurs to achieve a competitive advantage (Bennett, 2014; Dos Santos et al., 2019).

The analysis carried out with VOSviewer reveals the interconnections among keywords in research on female entrepreneurship and social media. Visualizing these connections helps to better understand the areas of interest, with studies grouped around the following themes: social media, gender, social aspects, general entrepreneurship, and the relationship between entrepreneurship and innovation. It can be stated that there is a trend toward discussing the use of social media, as well as gender and social impact issues, promoting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically SDG 5, which addresses gender equality and women's empowerment (Portal ODS, 2023). In practice, for the management of women-led businesses, the need for social media use to gain competitiveness is evident.

The article presented two limitations. The first concerns the number of articles found: 45 publications. Despite the limited number, they are relevant since they were published in A-rated journals according to CAPES. This fact highlights the relevance of the topic to research in the field of business, particularly entrepreneurship and marketing. The second limitation is that while the article showed that social media use is important for female entrepreneurship, it did not identify specific marketing practices. Future research may explore which social media platforms are most effective for each type of business, as well as which marketing strategies are most successful. In addition, future studies could

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examine which platforms women use most and what outcomes result from this use.

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REFERENCES

ABDELWAHID, Miriam; KAOUD, Hebatalla. Factors affecting the success of women entrepreneurs in Egypt. **International Journal of Organizational Leadership**, v. 11, n. 4, p. 444-461, 2022.

ALESSA, Adlah A. et al. Impact of COVID-19 on entrepreneurship and consumer behaviour: A case study in Saudi Arabia. **The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business**, v. 8, n. 5, p. 201-210, 2021.

ALHAKIMI, Wail; ALBASHIRI, Sumaya. Social media adoption by women entrepreneurial small businesses. **Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship**, v. 17, n. 3/4, p. 158-175, 2023.

ALJUWAIBER, Abobakr. Entrepreneurship research in the Middle East and North Africa: trends, challenges, and sustainability issues. **Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies**, v. 13, n. 3, p. 380-426, 2021.

ALKHOWAITER, Wassan. The power of Instagram in building small businesses. In: **Social Media: The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly: 15th IFIP WG 6.11 Conference on e-Business, e-Services, and e-Society, I3E 2016, Swansea, UK, September 13–15, 2016, Proceedings 15**. Springer International Publishing, 2016. p. 59-64.

ARACIL-JORDÁ, Jorge et al. Improving the social performance of women-led microenterprises: The role of social media marketing actions. **Technological Forecasting and Social Change**, v. 191, p. 122484, 2023.

BENDELL, Bari L.; SULLIVAN, Diane M.; HANEK, Kathrin J. Gender, technology and decision-making: insights from an experimental conjoint analysis. **International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research**, v. 26, n. 4, p. 647-670, 2020.

BENNETT, Lucy. Tracing textual poachers: Reflections on the development of fan studies and digital fandom. **Journal of Fandom Studies**, v. 2, n. 1, p. 5-20, 2014.

BLANCO-GONZALEZ-TEJERO, Cristina; CANO-MARIN, Enrique. Empowerment of women's entrepreneurship in family business through Twitter. **Journal of Family Business Management**, v. 13, n. 3, p. 607-625, 2023.

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BOUSSEMA, Samira. Role of passion in entrepreneurial responses to crises on social media platforms. **EuroMed Journal of Business**, 2023.

BRAHEM, Meriam; BOUSSEMA, Samira. Social media entrepreneurship as an opportunity for women: The case of Facebook-commerce. **The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation**, v. 24, n. 3, p. 191-201, 2023.

CAMACHO, Sonia; BARRIOS, Andrés. Social commerce affordances for female entrepreneurship: the case of Facebook. **Electronic Markets**, v. 32, n. 3, p. 1145-1167, 2022.

CHAKRABORTY, Uttam; BISWAL, Santosh Kumar. Impact of social media participation on female entrepreneurs towards their digital entrepreneurship intention and psychological empowerment. **Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship**, v. 25, n. 3, p. 374-392, 2023.

CHUEKE, Gabriel Vouga; AMATUCCI, Marcos. O que é bibliometria? Uma introdução ao Fórum. **Internext**, v. 10, n. 2, p. 1-5, 2015.

DA SILVA, Mariana Santos; LASSO, Sarah Venturim; MAINARDES, Emerson Wagner. Características do empreendedorismo feminino no Brasil. **Revista Gestão e Desenvolvimento**, v. 13, n. 2, p. 150-167, 2016.

DE SOUZA COSTA, Williana et al. O poder das redes sociais online nas manifestações ocorridas no Brasil. **Revista de Tecnologia Aplicada**, v. 5, n. 1, 2016.

DOS SANTOS, Juliana Medeiros et al. Mídias Digitais como Canal de Comunicação em Empresas do Ramo de Vestuário e Moda da Cidade de Santa Luzia/PB. **Conhecimento Interativo**, v. 13, n. 1, p. 330-345, 2019.

ETOGO, Gabriel; MANGA ENGAMA, Etgard; NOMO, Théophile Serge. Gender identities and corporate social responsibility practices: a biographical approach of managerial recompositions in SMEs context. **Social Responsibility Journal**, v. 18, n. 4, p. 772-786, 2022.

FLEURY, A. C. C.; FLEURY, M. T. L. **Estratégias empresariais e formação de competências**. São Paulo: Atlas, 2000.

RELISE

47

FONTANA, Darah de Mathias et al. Contribuições do uso de redes sociais virtuais para o empreendedorismo feminino. **Revista Ciências Administrativas**, v. 27, n. 1, 2021.

GEM - GLOBAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP MONITOR (2023). New GEM Women's Entrepreneurship Report Underscores Breaking Stereotypes and Seizing Opportunities. Disponível em: <<https://www.gemconsortium.org/reports/womens-entrepreneurship>>. Acesso em: 11/05/2024.

GENC, Merve; ÖKSÜZ, Burcu. A fact or an illusion: Effective social media usage of female entrepreneurs. **Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences**, v. 195, p. 293-300, 2015.

GHOUSE, Suhail et al. Barriers to rural women entrepreneurs in Oman. **International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research**, v. 23, n. 6, p. 998-1016, 2017.

GOLZARD, Vahideh. Economic empowerment of Iranian women through the internet. **Gender in Management: An International Journal**, v. 35, n. 1, p. 1-18, 2020.

GOMES, Bruna Laiene Tomacheski; MONDO, Tiago Savi. A contribuição das redes sociais na captação de clientes sob a percepção dos gestores hoteleiros. **Revista Brasileira de Marketing**, v. 15, n. 2, p. 195-206, 2016.

HALL, Paula; ELLIS, Debbie; MCARTHUR, Brian. Knowledge sharing enablers in small business networks. **International Journal of Knowledge Management (IJKM)**, v. 18, n. 1, p. 1-16, 2022.

HAMDANI, Nizar Alam et al. Gender stereotype perception, perceived social support and self-efficacy in increasing women's entrepreneurial intentions. **International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research**, v. 29, n. 6, p. 1290-1313, 2023.

HASHIM, Sumaya; NALDI, Lucia; MARKOWSKA, Magdalena. "The royal award goes to...": Legitimacy processes for female-led family ventures. **Journal of Family Business Strategy**, v. 12, n. 3, p. 100358, 2021.

RELISE

48

HU, Debao; ZHAI, Chenzhe; YAN, Zhen. Do social interactions foster household entrepreneurship? Evidence from online and offline data from China Family Panel Studies. **China Economic Review**, v. 79, p. 101965, 2023.

JABEEN, Fauzia et al. Determinants of innovation decisions among Emirati female-owned small and medium enterprises. **International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship**, v. 11, n. 4, p. 408-434, 2019.

JOSE, Saju. Strategic use of digital promotion strategies among female emigrant entrepreneurs in UAE. **International Journal of Emerging Markets**, v. 13, n. 6, p. 1699-1718, 2018.

KÉZAI, Petra Kinga; SZOMBATHELYI, Márta Konczos. Factors effecting female startappers in Hungary. **Economics & Sociology**, v. 14, n. 4, p. 186-203, 2021.

KHANG, Hyoungkoo; KI, Eyun-Jung; YE, Lan. Social media research in advertising, communication, marketing, and public relations, 1997–2010. **Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly**, v. 89, n. 2, p. 279-298, 2012.

KOTLER, P.; KELLER, K. L. **Administração de marketing**. 14^a. ed. São Paulo: Pearson Prentice Hall, 2012.

KOZUBÍKOVÁ, Ludmila; HOMOLKA, Lubor; KRISTALAS, Dimitris. The effect of business environment and entrepreneurs' gender on perception of financial risk in the SMEs sector. **Journal of Competitiveness**, 2017.

LE LOARNE–LEMAIRE, Séverine et al. Shaping entrepreneurial gender play: Intersubjectivity and performativity among female entrepreneurs. **Scandinavian Journal of Management**, v. 40, n. 1, p. 101316, 2024.

LOPES, Wesley Maique Oliveira; DE SOUZA FREITAS, Wesley Ricardo. Marketing ambiental: análise da produção científica brasileira. **Revista Brasileira de Marketing**, v. 15, n. 3, p. 355-372, 2016.

MEHTAP, Salime; OZMENEKSE, Leyla; CAPUTO, Andrea. “I’ma stay at home businesswoman”: an insight into informal entrepreneurship in Jordan. **Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies**, v. 11, n. 1, p. 44-65, 2019.

MENDONÇA, Marina Celia et al. The pain of an entrepreneur? Relationship between personality, life satisfaction, and psychological suffering of Brazilian

RELISE

49

entrepreneurs during the Covid19 pandemic. **International Journal of Innovation: IJI Journal**, v. 11, n. 1, p. 7, 2023.

MINIESY, Rania; FAKHRELDIN, Hadia. The impact of entrepreneurs' perceptions and social media usage on their intention to formalise their MSMEs in Egypt. **Journal of Entrepreneurship and Public Policy**, v. 12, n. 3/4, p. 209-233, 2023.

MINIESY, Rania; ELSHAHAWY, Engy; FAKHRELDIN, Hadia. Social media's impact on the empowerment of women and youth male entrepreneurs in Egypt. **International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship**, v. 14, n. 2, p. 235-262, 2022

NILSSON, Gabriella. Set in motion. Paradoxical narratives of becoming Swedish digital media influencers. **Gender, Work & Organization**, v. 31, n. 2, p. 337-352, 2024.

OKUBO, Yoshiko. **Bibliometric indicators and analysis of research systems: methods and examples**. 1997.

OLAMIDE, Akintimehin; OGBECHIE, Rose. Social capital and business performance: a study of female-owned SMEs in the Nigerian informal sector. **Small Enterprise Research**, v. 28, n. 2, p. 190-205, 2021.

OLSSON, Anna Karin; BERNHARD, Irène. Keeping up the pace of digitalization in small businesses—Women entrepreneurs' knowledge and use of social media. **International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research**, v. 27, n. 2, p. 378-396, 2021.

PERGELOVA, Albena et al. Democratizing entrepreneurship? Digital technologies and the internationalization of female-led SMEs. **Journal of Small Business Management**, v. 57, n. 1, p. 14-39, 2019.

PERGELOVA, Albena; ANGULO-RUIZ, Fernando; YORDANOVA, Desislava I. Gender and international entry mode. **International Small Business Journal**, v. 36, n. 6, p. 662-685, 2018.

PHAM, Tho; TALAVERA, Oleksandr. Discrimination, social capital, and financial constraints: The case of Viet Nam. **World Development**, v. 102, p. 228-242, 2018.

RELISE

50

PINOCHET, Luis Hernan Contreras; PACHELLI, Iara Louise; DA ROCHA, Francisco Marcelo Monteiro. Uso de Métricas em Mídias Sociais e Indicadores de Desempenho do Site e sua Relação com o Valor da Marca em Empresas de Cosméticos no Brasil. **Revista Brasileira de Marketing**, v. 17, n. 1, p. 80-99, 2018.

Portal ODS. Disponível em: <rd.portalods.com.br/relatorios/22/consumo-e-producao-responsavel/BRA004041095/curitiba---pr>. Acesso em: 11/05/2024.

POWELL, Gary N.; EDDLESTON, Kimberly A. Linking family-to-business enrichment and support to entrepreneurial success: do female and male entrepreneurs experience different outcomes?. **Journal of business venturing**, v. 28, n. 2, p. 261-280, 2013.

RAJAHONKA, Mervi; VILLMAN, Kaija. Women managers and entrepreneurs and digitalization: on the verge of a new era or a nervous breakdown?. **Technology Innovation Management Review**, v. 9, n. 6, 2019.

RAMADANI, Veland et al. Entrepreneurship education and graduates' entrepreneurial intentions: Does gender matter? A multi-group analysis using AMOS. **Technological Forecasting and Social Change**, v. 180, p. 121693, 2022.

RODNER, Victoria; GOODE, Amy; BURNS, Zara. "Is it all just lip service?": on Instagram and the normalisation of the cosmetic servicescape. **Journal of Services Marketing**, v. 36, n. 1, p. 44-58, 2022.

SARPONG, David; NYUUR, Richard; TORBOR, Mabel Kyeiwaa. Careers of commercially successful female entrepreneurs in context of underdeveloped markets and weak institutions. **International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research**, v. 28, n. 3, p. 698-719, 2022.

SEBRAE. **Tranformação digital das MPE 2018**. [S. l.]: Sebrae 2018.

SEREDKINA, Elena; BUROVA, Olga; GANINA, Olga. Women Entrepreneurship in the Time of COVID19 Pandemic: Opportunities and Risks (The Case of Perm Region, Russia). **Journal of Women's Entrepreneurship & Education**, 2021.

SHASTRI, Swati et al. Exploring women entrepreneurs' motivations and challenges from an institutional perspective: Evidences from a patriarchal state

RELISE

51

in India. **Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy**, v. 16, n. 4, p. 653-674, 2022.

STEPHAN, Ute; ZBIEROWSKI, Przemyslaw; HANARD, Pierre-Jean. Entrepreneurship and Covid-19: Challenges and opportunities. **KBS Covid-19 research impact papers**, v. 2, p. 1-30, 2020.

SULTAN, Suhail; SULTAN, Wasim IM. Women MSMEs in times of crisis: challenges and opportunities. **Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development**, v. 27, n. 7, p. 1069-1083, 2020.

TOKBAEVA, Dinara. Female founders in post-socialist contexts: A case study of female founders and owners of media businesses in Kyrgyzstan. **Women in management in Central and Eastern European countries**, p. 172-183, 2020.

TOVMASYAN, Gayane. Promoting female entrepreneurship in tourism for sustainable development. **Marketing i menedžment inovacij**, n. 1, p. 18-36, 2022.

TREQUATTRINI, Raffaele et al. Social media as a new opportunity for female entrepreneurs: An analysis of the fashion industry. In: **Advances in Gender and Cultural Research in Business and Economics: 4th IPAZIA Workshop on Gender Issues 2018, Rome, Italy 4**. Springer International Publishing, 2019. p. 287-298.

UN WOMEN (2020). How COVID-19 impacts women and girls. Disponível em: <https://interactive.unwomen.org/multimedia/explainer/covid19/en/index.html?gclid=Cj0KCQiArvX_BRCyARIsAKsnTxMCmmRLVHIJZKH0aJUhUG_EpPb1VrNIYMrBzZYdBq0TPqzsWINLGJYaAhD8EALw_wcB>. Acesso em: 27/02/2024.

VENDRAMINE, Maraf de Feritas Maio; NOBRE, Fábio Chaves; VIEIRA, Almir Martins. Como enfrentar a Covid-19?. **Revista Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração**, v. 15, n. 1, p. 197-211, 2021.